

Biodegradation of 2,4-dimethylpyridine by *Rhodococcus erythropolis*

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The process of biodegradation of 2,4-dimethylpyridine by bacterium Rhodococcus erythropolis 2.4DMP accompanied by the formation of four metabolites - 4,6-dimethylpyridin-3-ol, pyridine-2,4-dicarboxylic acid, (3E)-3-(formylimino)prop-1-ene-1,1,3-tricarboxylic acid and (3E)-3-(formylimino)-2-hydroxyprop-1-ene-1,1,3-tricarboxylic acid.

Keywords: *biodegradation, 2,4-dimethylpyridine, Rhodococcus erythropolis, bacteria*

Introduction

Intensive development of the chemical industry led to the fact that the biosphere constantly receives polluting substances. Very hazardous pollutants are heterocyclic organic compounds. Pyridine and its derivatives are an important class of heterocyclic compounds [1]. They are formed during coal processing and contained in wastewater chemical plants, plants of the production of synthetic rubber, plastics, dyes [2-4]. Pure pyridines are widely used as solvents and reactants in the production of agricultural chemicals, such as herbicides and also pharmaceuticals [5].

Materials and methods

The object of the researches served the strain of the bacterium *R. erythropolis* 2.4DMP obtained from the collection of microorganisms of the Department of Microbiology, Moscow State University.

To study of the degradation of 2,4-dimethylpyridine (**I**) was used the synthetic medium having the following composition (g/L): Na₂HPO₄ – 4.26; KH₂PO₄ – 2.65; MgSO₄·7H₂O – 0.2; FeSO₄·7H₂O – 0.01; CaCl₂·2H₂O – 0.02;

MnSO₄·H₂O – 0.002; Na₂MoO₄ – 0.001; deionised water – 1 L; pH 7.0 – 7.2. Cultivation was carried out in flasks (750 ml) with 200 ml of a medium on a shaker (200 rpm/min) at 28-30°C.

As the source of carbon and nitrogen in the liquid medium was added 2.0 g/L 2,4-dimethylpyridine. The degradation process was performed for 36 hours.

Degradation products were extracted with chloroform and after evaporation were dissolved in 0.5-1.0 ml of ethanol and had been conducting separating on chromatographic plates of "Silufol UV-254" (DC-Alufolies Kieselgel 60 F254, Merck, Germany). For chromatography were used the following solvent systems:

1. chloroform - methanol (20:3);
2. chloroform - acetone - ethanol (7:2:2);
3. ethanol - ammonia - water (20:1:4);
4. ethyl acetate - petroleum ether (5:1).

Chromatograms were visualized in UV light or iodine vapors. For the preparative isolation of individual products was used column chromatography (Silicagel L 40/100, Chemapol, Czech Republic) in a solvent system 3, and preparative thin layer chromatography in solvent systems 2, 3 and 4. Electron ionization (EI) mass spectrometry was performed at an electron energy of 70 eV on the instrument Finigan MAT-4615. ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectral analyses were performed at 60 MHz Tesla BS-467 (Czech Republic) NMR spectrometer operating at 28°C. Compounds were dissolved in CDCl₃.

Results and discussion

As a result, bioconversion 2,4-dimethylpyridine (Fig. 1) was isolated substance **II** and identified as 4,6-dimethylpyridin-3-ol.

Compound **II** has been accumulating in the log phase (18-20 hours) and decreases in the stationary phase (30 hours). The structure of the compound **II** was established on the basis of the ¹H NMR spectrum. In the ¹H NMR spectrum

was observed singlet of proton H-2 with a chemical shift of 7.63 ppm, singlet of proton H-5 with a chemical shift of 7.00 ppm and two singlets with three protons (4-CH₃ and 6-CH₃ - groups) with a chemical shifts of 2.30 ppm and 2.50 ppm, respectively. In the spectrum also was present the singlet of the proton of OH-group present as a broadened signal with chemical shift of 6.20 ppm The structure of the compound correspond to the formula on the Table 1.

Chromatographic analysis of the extract of the culture liquid from the stationary growth phase showed the presence of a pyridine-2,4-dicarboxylic acid (**III**), which was obtained as dibutyl ester, and identified as the dibutyl pyridine-2,4-dicarboxylate (**IIIa**, Table 2).

Also, in extracts of the culture liquid were found carboxylic acids **IV** and **V**. Compounds **IV** and **V** were found only in extracts of culture fluid of logarithmic phase of growth bacteria. By the results of the mass spectra analysis of compound **IV** in the form of its [(2E)-3-[2-(2,4-diaminophenyl)hydrazinyl]-2-(formylimino)-3-oxopropylidene]propanedioic acid (**IVa**) (Table 3) it was identified as the (3E)-3-(formylimino)prop-1-ene-1,1,3-tricarboxylic acid (**IV**).

Table 1. Mass spectrum of 4,6-dimethylpyridin-3-ol (**II**)

Structure of compound II	<i>m/z</i>	Relative abundance, %	The formation of fragments
	123	100	[M ⁺]
	122	7	[M ⁺ - H]
	107	7	[M ⁺ - H-CH ₃]
	104	7	[M ⁺ - H ₂ -H ₂ O]
	94	15	[M ⁺ - CHO]
	93	48	[M ⁺ - H-CHO]
	81	7	[M ⁺ - H-CH ₃ -CN]
	80	7	[M ⁺ - H-CH ₃ -HCN]

By the results of the mass spectra analysis of compound **V** in the form of its [(2E)-3-[2-(2,4-diaminophenyl)hydrazinyl]-2-(formylimino)-1-hydroxy-3-oxopropylidene]propanedioic acid (**Va**) (Table 4) it was identified as the (3E)-3-(formylimino)-2-hydroxyprop-1-ene-1,1,3-tricarboxylic acid (**V**).

Table 2. Mass spectrum of dibutyl pyridine-2,4-dicarboxylate (**IIIa**)

Structure of compound IIIa	<i>m/z</i>	Relative abundance, %	The formation of fragments
	279	5	[M] ⁺
	206	12	[M ⁺ - C ₄ H ₉ O]
	150	100	[M ⁺ - C ₄ H ₉ O - C ₄ H ₈]
	133	8	[M ⁺ - C ₄ H ₉ O - C ₄ H ₉ O]
	122	4	[M ⁺ - C ₄ H ₉ O - C ₄ H ₈ - CO]
	94	6	[M ⁺ - C ₄ H ₉ O - C ₄ H ₈ - 2CO]

By the end of the cultivation of compounds **IV** and **V** were not observed in culture liquid, that indicates that it is intermediate products.

The structures of the two isolated tricarboxylic acids point on disclosure hydroxylated pyridine ring (**II**), whose two methyl groups are oxidized to carbonyl groups, between C-5 and C-6 atoms of carbon. The degradation of 2,4-dimethylpyridine (**I**) is shown in Fig. 1.

Table 3. Mass spectrum of [(2E)-3-[2-(2,4-diaminophenyl)hydrazinyl]-2-(formylimino)-3-oxopropylidene]propanedioic acid (**IVa**)

Structure of compound IVa	m/z	Relative abundance, %	The formation of fragments
	412	100	[M ⁺ +NH ₃]
	395	54	[M] ⁺
	394	53	[M ⁺ - H]
	378	29	[M ⁺ - OH]
	377	67	[M ⁺ - H - OH]
	366	16	[M ⁺ -CHO]
	351	80	[M ⁺ - CO ₂]
	349	33	[M ⁺ - NO ₂]
	347	20	[M ⁺ - H-OH-NO]
	30	86	[M ⁺ - H-2OH-NO]
	317	30	[M ⁺ - H-OH-2NO-CO]
	289	32	[M ⁺ - H-OH-NO-CO]
	232	9	[M ⁺ - H-OH-NO-CH=C(COOH ₂) ₂]
	229	8	[M ⁺ - C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]
	214	6	[M ⁺ -NC ₆ H ₃ (NO ₂) ₂]
170	8	[M ⁺ -CONHNHC ₆ H ₃ (NO ₂) ₂]	

However, our study did not allow to determine which process is the primary - hydroxylation of the ring or oxidation of the methyl groups.

Usually process of bacterial hydroxylation of organic compounds carried out with help of dioxygenases [6], in same time the eukaryotic microbes (fungi) carried out the processes of hydroxylation with using of monooxygenases [7-11].

Table 4. Mass spectrum of [(2E)-3-[2-(2,4-diaminophenyl)hydrazinyl]-2-(formylimino)-1-hydroxy-3-oxopropylidene]propanedioic acid (**Va**)

Structure of compound Va	<i>m/z</i>	Relative abundance, %	The formation of fragments
	428	100	[M ⁺ +NH ₃]
	411	5	[M] ⁺
	410	5	[M ⁺ -H]
	394	15	[M ⁺ -OH]
	393	5	[M ⁺ -H-OH]
	367	7	[M ⁺ -CO ₂]
	366	15	[M ⁺ -COOH]
	365	10	[M ⁺ -NO ₂]
	363	6	[M ⁺ -H-OH-NO ₂]
	351	24	[M ⁺ -H-OH-NCO]
	347	17	[M ⁺ -H-OH-NO ₂]
	332	10	[M ⁺ -H-OH-2NO]
	304	20	[M ⁺ -H-H ₂ O-2NO CO]
	232	95	[M ⁺ -H-OH-NO-C(OH)=C(COOH) ₂]
	230	16	[M ⁺ -NC ₆ H ₃ (NO ₂) ₂]
	214	62	[M ⁺ -H-OH-NO-C=C(COOH) ₂ -H ₂ O]
	168	15	[C ₆ H ₄ ((NO ₂) ₂) ⁺ ·

Fig. 1. The process of catabolism of 2,4-dimethylpyridine (**I**) by strain *R. erythropolis* 2.4DMP. **II** - 4,6-dimethylpyridin-3-ol; **III** - pyridine-2,4-dicarboxylic acid; **IV** - (3E)-3-(formylimino)prop-1-ene-1,1,3-tricarboxylic acid; **V** - (3E)-3-(formylimino)-2-hydroxyprop-1-ene-1,1,3-tricarboxylic acid.

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